

Recovery of antioxidant enzymes by red grape extract due to Nicotine induced changes in the liver tissue of male albino rats with reference to the aging

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ABSTRACT

The beneficial effects of Red grape (*Vitis vinifera*) extract as an antioxidant has been assessed in nicotine administered rats to examine the effects of nicotine on the antioxidant defense systems in liver tissue of male albino rat. Age matched rats were divided into 4 groups of six in each group and treated as follows: Group I. Normal Control (NC) (Control rats received 0.9% saline). Group II. Nicotine treated (Nt) (at a dose of 0.6 mg/kg body weight by subcutaneous injection for a period of 2 months). Group III. Red grape extract treated (RGEt). (Red grape extract at a doses of 50 mg/kg body weight via orogastric tube for a period of 2 months). Group IV. Nicotine + Red grape extract treated (Nt+RGEt) (The forth group of rats were received the nicotine + red grape extract as followed by the second and third group). The animals were sacrificed after 24 hours after the last treatment by cervical dislocation and isolated the liver tissue washed with ice-cold saline, immediately immersed in liquid nitrogen and stored at -800 C for biochemical analysis and enzymatic assays. In the present study the Superoxide dismutase (SOD), Catalase (CAT), Glutathione (GSH) and Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) were significantly decreased in nicotine treated rats in the liver tissue and enhance was observed in the combination treatment (Nt+RGEt), The data obtained from this study speculated that 50 mg of RGEt has the capacity to scavenge free radical and can protect against oxidative stress induced by Nicotine intoxication. Supplementation of RGEt could be useful in alleviating antioxidant enzymes in nicotine induced liver injury rats.

Keywords: Nicotine, Red Grape Extract, Superoxide dismutase (SOD), Catalase (CAT), Glutathione (GSH) and Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px), Liver tissue and Male albino rats.

INTRODUCTION

Red Grape (*Vitis vinifera* L.) presumably originates from Western Asia, from the areas between the Caspian Sea region and Asia Minor, where also its cultivation seems to have begun (Bombardelli *et al.*, 1995; Johnson, 1989). These Archeological finds, up to this day the oldest documentation for the use of grape vine products in human culture, were dated to 3500 - 2900 B.C. (McGovern, 1995). Today, *Vitis vinifera* has

reached all continents but is successfully cultivated only in temperate climate regions with warm and dry summers and relatively mild winters with sufficient rain (Bombardelli *et al.*, 1995). In the past few years there has been an increasing interest in determining relevant dietary sources of antioxidant phenolics. Red Grape (*Vitis vinifera*) is among the fruits with the highest content of these compounds. A large amount of different phenolic compounds is present in skin, pulp and seeds, and they also undergo partial extraction during winemaking processes (Revilla and Ryan, 2000).

Figure-1: Medicinal properties of grapes and their ingredients.

Consumption of grape flavonoids has been shown to confer antioxidant protection, (Figure-1) inhibit platelet activity, reduce thrombus formation and leads to the concentration of inflammatory biomarkers (Castilla *et al.*, 2006; O'Byrne *et al.*, 2002). This effect may be considered to be beneficial for the prevention of cardiovascular disease (Castilla *et al.*, 2006). *In vitro* studies showed that grape juice has significant antioxidant activity and can inhibit oxidation of low density lipoprotein (LDL) (Castilla *et al.*, 2006; O'Byrne *et al.*, 2002). In addition to their antioxidant activity, polyphenols also possess many different biological properties that may contribute to their cardio-protective effects, including the ability to inhibit platelet activity and thrombosis (Demrow *et al.*, 1995; Freedman *et al.*, 2001). *In vivo* studies showed that administration of dealcoholized red wine (Vinson, 2001). Grape extracts may also spare the endogenous enzymes responsible for protecting against oxidative damage. These *in vitro* and animal studies suggest that human consumption of grape extracts may offer protection against oxidative stress. Oxidative stress is a hallmark of various health problems. Resveratrol (3,5,40-trans-trihydroxystilbene) is a natural phytoalexin abundantly found in grapes and red wine, which has potent antioxidant property.

Nicotine is a naturally occurring alkaloid found in the nightshade family (*Solanaceae*) of plants, predominantly in tobacco plant (*Nicotiana tabacum*) (Wu *et al.*, 2002). Hellermann *et al.*, (2002). Tobacco generally refers to the leaves and other parts of plants that have been domesticated and used to obtain the alkaloid nicotine. In most mammalian species, nicotine is rapidly and extensively metabolized, primarily in the liver (Kyerematen and Vesell, 1991). The major metabolic pathways of nicotine in mammals are C-oxidation and N-oxidation, *i.e.* cotinine and nicotine N'-oxide formation, respectively. Cotinine formation from nicotine is a two-step reaction in mammals. The first step is the conversion of nicotine to nicotine- $\Delta^{1(5)}$ -iminium ion by CYP. The second step, the conversion of the iminium ion to cotinine, is mediated by cytosolic aldehyde oxidase (Kyerematen and Vesell, 1991). About 4% of nicotine is converted to nicotine N'-oxide, which is largely excreted in urine without further metabolism (Jacob *et al.*, 1988). Nicotine is known to induced oxidative stress and depletes antioxidant defense mechanisms; produced reduction in glutathione peroxidase in circulation, lung, liver and kidney of nicotine-treated animals (Yildiz, 2004; Muthukumaran *et al.*, 2008). Nicotine also increases both free fatty acid release from the liver and the hepatic

synthesis of very low-density lipoproteins; also maternal nicotine exposure induced oxidative stress and causes histopathological changes in the lung and liver of lactating offspring (El-Sokkary *et al.*, 2007).

After absorption into the blood, which is at pH 7.4, about 69 percent of the nicotine is ionized and 31 percent nonionized. Binding to plasma proteins is less than 5 percent (Benowitz, Jacob *et al.*, 1982). Nicotine is extensively metabolized, primarily in the liver, but also to a small extent in the lung (Turner *et al.*, 1975). Renal excretion of unchanged nicotine depends on urinary pH and urine flow, and may range from 2 to 35 percent, but typically accounts for 5 to 10 percent of total elimination (Benowitz, Kuyt *et al.*, 1983; Rosenberg *et al.*, 1980).

Table-1. Steady state distribution of nicotine

Tissue	Tissue to blood ratio
Blood	1.0
Brain	3.0
Heart	3.7
Muscle	2.0
Adipose	0.5
Kidney	21.6
Liver	3.7
Lung	2.0
Gastrointestinal	3.5

Source: BENOWITZ, N.L. Human pharmacology of nicotine. In: Cappell, H.D. *et al.*, (eds.) *Research advances in Alcohol and Drug Problems*, Volume 9. New York: Plenum Press, 1986b.

Liver is an important organ that has many tasks, and is responsible for processing drugs, alcohol and other toxins to remove them from the body. Nicotine from heavy smoking increases the risk of developing hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), (El -Zayadi, 2006). Smoking increases the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines involved in liver cell injury (Moszczynski *et al.*,

2001). It has been reported that smoking increases fibrosis score and histological activity index in chronic hepatitis C (CHC) patients (Pessione *et al.*, 2001) and contributes to progression of HBV-related cirrhosis (Yu *et al.*, 1997). Like other organs of the body, liver structure and functions are also altered with age advances. Nevertheless, an age related decrease in the expression of several genes involved in mitochondrial bioenergetics and mitochondrial biogenesis occurs in aging mice, the largest age associated alteration affects the matrix enzyme Lon protease (Lee *et al.*, 1999).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animals:

Pathogen free, wistar strain male albino rats of two age groups (3 months and 18 months) 3 months age group considered as 'Young age' and 18 months age group considered as 'Old age' as per the life span of Wistar strain male albino rats (Jang *et al.*, 2001) were used in the present study. The usage of animals was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (No: 19/2012-2013/(i)/a/CPCSEA/IAEC/SVU/KC/SVU/KC/RSS, dt. 01.07.2012). The rats were housed in clean polypropylene cages under hygienic conditions with photoperiod of 12 hours light and 12 hours dark. The rats were fed with standard laboratory chow (Hindustan Lever Ltd, Mumbai) and water *ad libitum*.

Procurement of chemicals:

All the chemicals used in the present study were Analytical grade (AR) and obtained from the following scientific companies: Sigma (St. Louis, MO, USA), Fisher (Pittsburg, PA, USA), Merck (Mumbai, India), Ranbaxy (New Delhi, India), Qualigens (Mumbai, India).

Dosage of nicotine:

The dose administration of nicotine was followed as per the protocol given by (Shoaib and Stoleran, 1999; Helen *et al.*, 2003) 0.6 mg / kg body weight (0.5ml) was chosen as the dose, for this study.

Red Grape Collection and Extraction

Red Grapes, as large clusters with red berries, were brought from local surroundings in Bangalore and identified as *Vitis vinifera* L. (Family *Vitaceae*). The grape were crushed (whole fruit) for juice and dried in shade, powdered and extract by maceration with 70% alcoholic for 72 hours in ambient temperature. The Red Grape extract was filtered and then solvent evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure in a rotary evaporator. The residual Red Grape extract was used for this study.

Treatment schedule:

Age matched rats divided into 4 groups of six in each group and treated as follows:

Group-1. Control rats (Rats received 0.9% saline).

Group-2. Nicotine treatment (Nt) (Rats were received the nicotine at a dose of 0.6 mg/kg body weight by subcutaneous injection for a period of 2 months).

Group-3. Red Grape Extract treatment (RGEt) (Rats were received red grape extract 50mg/kg body weight via orogastric tube for a period of 2 months).

Group-4. Nicotine+Red grape extract (Nt+RGEt) (Rats were received the nicotine at a dose of 0.6 mg/kg body weight by subcutaneous injection and red grape extract 50mg/kg body weight via orogastric tube for a period of 2 months).

The animals were sacrificed after 24 hrs after the last treatment session by cervical dislocation and the liver tissue was isolated at -4°C , washed with ice-cold saline, immediately immersed in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C , for biochemical analysis and enzymatic assays. Before assay, the tissues were thawed, sliced and homogenized under ice-cold conditions. Selected parameters were estimated by employing standard methods.

Biochemical Investigation:

In the present study Superoxide dismutase (SOD), Catalase (CAT), Glutathione (GSH) and Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) were analyzed. Superoxide dismutase activity was determined according to the method of Misra and Fridovich (1972). The SOD Activity expressed as the amount of enzyme that inhibits

the oxidation of epinephrine by 50%, which is equal to 1 unit. Catalase activity was measured by a slightly modified version of Aebi (1984). One unit of activity is equal to the moles of H_2O_2 degraded / mg protein / min. Glutathione content was determined according to the method of Theodorou *et. al.*, (1981). The glutathione content was expressed in nano moles / gram wet weight of the tissue. Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) was determined by a modified version of Flohe and Gunzler (1984). One unit of activity is equal to the mM of NADPH oxidized / mg protein / min. The enzyme activity was expressed in μ moles of NADPH oxidized / mg protein / min.

Statistical Analysis:

Statistical analysis has been carried out using INSTAT software. The data was analyzed for the significance; the results were presented with the P-value.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Superoxide dismutase:

In the present study the Superoxide dismutase activity was significantly decreased ($P < 0.01$) in both age groups (young and old) of nicotine treated rats (young by -27.95 %; old by -16.80%) when compared to the control rats. In Red Grape Extract treated rats of both age groups (young and old) significantly an increase ($P < 0.01$) was observed when compared to the control rats (young by 13.32 %; old by 10.41 %). In the combination treatment (Nt+RGEt) non significantly an increase was observed when compared to the control rats of both age groups. (Table-1).

In the present study a decrease was absorbed in SOD activity in the liver tissue of both age groups, due to nicotine treatment. The present results in the current investigation are in consistence with the previous findings. Among the generated free radicals due to nicotine metabolism, superoxide anion is the first derived free radical from nicotine. Thus, increased generation of superoxide radicals caused oxidative stress and damages the liver cells. In fact SOD scavenges the superoxide radicals in

Table–1: Changes in Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity due to Nicotine treatment (Nt), Red Grape Extract treatment (RGEt) and interaction of the both (Nt+RGEt) for a period of 2 months over the control in Liver tissue of male albino rats of young (3 months) and old (18 months) age groups. Values are expressed in units of Superoxide anion reduced/ mg proteins.

Name of the tissue	Young				Old			
	Control	Nt	RGEt	Nt+RGEt	Control	Nt	RGEt	Nt+RGEt
Liver	166.21 ±7.08	119.75** ±4.52 (-27.95)	188.36** ±6.01 (+13.32)	171.30@ ±6.59 (+3.06)	164.18 ±3.94	136.59** ±5.81 (-16.80)	181.28** ±5.25 (+10.41)	168.40@ ±4.28 (+2.57)

All the values are ± SD of six individual observations.

Values in parentheses denote per cent change over respective control.

* Values are significant at P < 0.05; ** Values are significant at P < 0.01; @ Values are non-significant.

the tissues. In addition, the over production of superoxide radicals due to nicotine intoxication implies the over utilization of SOD, this may indicate its low activity under nicotine induced

oxidative stress condition. The decrease in SOD activity due to nicotine consumption may impairs the other antioxidant enzyme activities like catalase and glutathione peroxidase. Because the superoxide radicals that are produced in the liver during nicotine metabolism are quickly scavenged to H₂O₂ by the enzyme superoxide dismutase. Under these circumstances, if SOD is not detoxifying the superoxide radical to hydrogen peroxide, there would be deficiency of substrate i.e., H₂O₂ for catalase and glutathione peroxidase enzyme activities. Thus, this kind of situation leads to impair the other antioxidant enzymes in the tissue metabolism.

Similar studies have been reported by several authors, Chennaiah *et al.*, (2006) reported due to nicotine treatment SOD activity was decrease in the muscle tissue. The depletion of SOD activity was may be due to dispose of the free radical, produced by the nicotine toxicity. Khalindhar Basha *et al.*,(2013) reported in the kidney tissue the Superoxide dismutase activity was decreased due to nicotine toxicity. Helen *et al.*, (2000) reported the decreased SOD activity in brain tissue of rat due to nicotine toxicity. EI- Sokkary *et al.*, (2007) reported chronic administration of

nicotine the SOD activity was decreased the rat liver and lung. Chattopadhyay and Chattopadhyay (2008) reported due to nicotine treatment the SOD activity was decreased in Ovary tissue. Similar changes in SOD activity was reported in various toxic conditions.

Mahendran and Syamala Devi, (2001) reported decrease in SOD activity with 18% ethanol treatment in the hepatic tissue. Somani and Husain, (1997b) reported significant decrease in plasma and hepatic SOD activity with 20% of chronic ethanol treatment. When alcohol is metabolized in the liver by the MEOS pathway, a potentially dangerous by products such as, acetaldehyde and cytotoxic free radicals are generated (Temel *et al.*, 2002; Lieber, 2004). Evidences are exist that ethanol intake increases the oxidative stress in the liver (Nordmann, 1994; Chen and Cohen, 1995) and its toxicity is associated with elevated generation of reactive oxygen species (Reinke *et al.*, 1994). Among the generated free radicals due to ethanol metabolism, superoxide anion is the first derived free radical from ethanol. Thus, increased generation of superoxide radicals caused oxidative stress and damages the liver cells. Nordmann, (1994) showed that an acute ethanol load significantly enhanced superoxide generation in rat liver sub-mitochondrial particles.

In the present study liver SOD activity was significantly increased with Red Grape extract treatment in both age groups of rats. This elevation was more pronounced in young age rats than old age rats. Khalindhar Basha *et al.*, (2013) reported in the kidney tissue SOD activity was enhanced in Red grape extract treated rats. *In vitro* studies showed that grape juice has significant antioxidant activity and can inhibit oxidation of low density lipoprotein (LDL) (Castilla *et al.*, 2006; O'Byrne *et al.*, 2002). In addition to their antioxidant activity, polyphenols also possess many different biological properties. Normally phenolic compounds act by scavenging free radicals and quenching the lipid peroxidative side chain. It has been proposed that hydroxyl and hydroperoxy radicals initiate hydrogen abstraction from a free phenolic substrate to form phenoxy radicals that can rearrange to quinone methide radical intermediates which is excreted via bile (Rukkumani *et al.*, 2004). Dani *et al.*, (2008) reported the SOD activity was increased in rats when treated with organic grape juice. The activities of two major antioxidant enzymes, mitochondria SOD and cytosolic glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) were higher in Red Grape Extract treated animals than the control animals. The increased generation of free radicals i.e., superoxide anion radicals would have triggered the induction of SOD enzyme and hence SOD activity was elevated during Red Grape extract treatment. Among the various antioxidant enzymes SOD provides the first line of defense against superoxide radicals, elevated SOD activity may reduce the exposure of the

hepatic tissue to superoxide radicals and perhaps hydroxyl radicals formed via the *Haber-Weiss* reaction (Halliwell and Gutteridge, 1989). In the present investigation increased liver SOD activity during Red Grape extract treatment helps in preventing accumulation of superoxide anion radicals in the tissue of old age rats by converting them to H₂O₂ which is considered to be an adaptational change by Red Grape Extract treatment to mitigate superoxide toxicity.

This study supported a long standing hypothesis that generation of oxygen derived free radicals and other reactive oxidants may be increased in aged liver tissue. These results were also agreed with previous findings, which reported the decreased SOD activity with advancement of age (Rao *et al.*, 1990). Vohra *et al.*, (2001) reported the decrease in SOD activity in brain regions of 36 months old age guinea pigs. The reported decrease in SOD activity with age may further accelerated the aging process (Carillo *et al.*, 1992). Miquel, (1980) and others postulated that mitochondrial decay is a significant factor in aging, caused, in part, by the release of reactive oxygen species (ROS) as byproducts of mitochondrial electron transport. Several authors quoted that during aging, inner mitochondrial membrane being a major intracellular site for the generation of superoxide anion radicals, which are toxic to the body (Yan and Sohal, 1998; Bejma and Ji, 1999). Mitochondria are the targets of oxidant byproducts. The steady state and the percentage of oxygen converted to superoxide anion radical increased with age (Sohal *et al.*, 1995; Perez *et al.*, 1998; Sastre *et*

Table-2: Changes in Catalase (CAT) activity due to Nicotine treatment (Nt) ,Red Grape Extract treatment (RGEt) and interaction of the both (Nt+RGEt) for a period of 2 months over the control in Liver tissue of male albino rats of young (3 months) and old (18 months) age groups. Values are expressed in μ moles of H₂O₂ cleaved/mg protein/min.

Name of the tissue	Young				Old			
	Control	Nt	RGEt	Nt+RGEt	Control	Nt	RGEt	Nt+RGEt
Liver	124.46 ±4.64	89.52** ±4.99 (-28.07)	132.53** ±5.70 (+6.48)	125.33@ ±5.85 (+0.69)	117.35 ±5.70	87.04** ±5.06 (-25.82)	122.31** ±4.14 (+4.22)	119.63@ ±4.54 (+1.94)

All the values are \pm SD of six individual observations.

Values in parentheses denote per cent change over respective control.

* Values are significant at P < 0.05; ** Values are significant at P < 0.01; @ Values are non-significant.

al., 2000). SOD activity may also reduce in aging rats due to over utilization of SOD to counter the age induced free radicals in the liver tissue. Moderate Red Grape Extract treatment produce a beneficial effect by decreasing the levels of oxidative stress markers in the mitochondria of liver and prevent the age associated decrease of antioxidant enzyme activities in the same organ. In the combination treatment (Nt+RGEt) was observed the upregulation of antioxidant enzyme activity, decrease in oxidative stress and increased activity of mitochondrial electron transfer enzymes, are logically related.

Catalase:

In the present study the Catalase activity was significantly decreased ($P < 0.01$) in both age groups (young and old) of nicotine treated rats (young by -28.07%; old by -25.82%) when compared to the control rats. In Red Grape Extract treated rats of both age groups (young and old) significantly an increase ($P < 0.01$) was observed when compared to the control rats (young by 6.48%; old by 4.22%). In the combination treatment (Nt+RGEt) non significantly increase was observed when compared to the control rats of both age groups. (Table-2).

In the present study we found that the administration of nicotine observed the decrease in CAT activity in the liver tissue. Similar studies have been reported by several authors. Chennaiah *et al.*, (2006) reported due to nicotine treatment CAT activity was decreased in the muscle tissue. Khalindhar Basha *et al.*, (2013) reported CAT activity was reduced in the Kidney tissue due to nicotine toxicity. Helen *et al.*, (2000) reported the decreased CAT activity in brain tissue of rat due to nicotine toxicity. Avati *et al.*, (2006) reported chronic administration of nicotine the CAT activity was decreased in the rat liver, lung and kidney. The depletion of CAT activity was may be due to dispose of the free radical, produced by the nicotine toxicity. Similar changes in CAT activity was reported in various toxic conditions by varies authors. Bindu *et al.*, (2002) reported the decrease in CAT activity with 4g/kg body weight alcohol

treatment for a period of 50 days in Sprague Dawley albino rats. Recently Das and Vasudevan, (2005b) reported a significant decrease in CAT activity with 2g /kg body weight ethanol treatment for a period of 4 weeks in hepatic tissue of Wistar strain male albino rats. This ethanol induced decrease in CAT activity may be due to enzyme protein oxidation as a result of accumulation of H_2O_2 and other cytotoxic radicals (Somani *et al.*, 1996). In alcoholism, hepatic catalase activities decline; it appears to be altered in iron over load (Bondy and Orozco, 1994). The decreased CAT activity with ethanol treatment indicates inefficient scavenging of hydrogen peroxide due to oxidative inactivation of enzyme. Husain and Somani, (1997a) reported a significant decrease in plasma CAT activity in alcohol treated rats. The lower levels of plasma CAT activity may be explained due to mobilization of iron, which can generate ROS and these species can release low molecular weight iron (Nordmann, *et al.*, 1987). The two antioxidant enzymes namely SOD and CAT decreased significantly in the hepatic tissue of alcohol administered rats suggesting the increased damage to this tissue as a result of uncontrolled generation of partially reduced oxygen species (Mahendran and Shyamala Devi, 2001).

In the present study, in the both age groups of Red Grape extract treatment (RGEt) rats the CAT activity was increased. Similar studies has been reported in the kidney tissue CAT activity was enhanced in the red grape extract treatment rats (Khalindhar Basha *et al.*, 2013). The increased catalase activity indicates its active involvement in the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide during Red Grape extract treatment. A change in the binding characteristics of enzyme to membrane or their release from peroxisomes has been proposed as a possible mechanism for the increased activity levels of CAT (Somani and Rayback, 1996). CAT and SOD are considered to be indispensable for the survival of the cell against deleterious effects of hydroperoxides. The combination of SOD and CAT provide an efficient mechanism for removal of free radicals from the cell (Husain *et al.*, 1996; Bhaskar Reddy, 2002). In *in vitro* studies

showed that grape juice has significant antioxidant activity and can inhibit oxidation of low density lipoprotein (LDL) (Castilla *et al.*, 2006; O'Byrne *et al.*, 2002). In addition to their antioxidant activity, polyphenols also possess many different biological properties. Normally phenolic compounds act by scavenging free radicals and quenching the lipid peroxidative side chain. It has been proposed that hydroxyl and hydroperoxy radicals initiate hydrogen abstraction from a free phenolic substrate to form phenoxy radicals that can rearrange to quinone methide radical intermediates which is excreted via bile (Rukkumani *et al.*, 2004). Similar studies have been reported by several authors. Dani *et al.*, (2008) reported the CAT activity was increased in rats when treated with organic grape juice.

In the current investigation, catalase activity was decreased with advancement of age. The decreased CAT activity in old age animals may be due to increase in the oxidative stress with age. Demaree *et al.*, (1999) reported the decreased aortic CAT activity in old age rats than in young rats. It was observed that decline in SOD activity with age may result in lower CAT activity in the hepatic tissue. Rao *et al.*, (1990) reported that the CAT activity was decreased in the tissues of liver, brain and kidney with aging. They also reported mRNA levels in the tissues of aged rats, which may result in the decreased activity of the enzyme in aged rats. Matsuo *et al.*, (1992) also reported decreased CAT activity in the liver tissue between, 8, 14 and 32 months aged rats. The

rates of mitochondrial superoxide and H₂O₂ generation were found to increase with age in mammals (Sohal *et al.*, 1990; Jhansi Lakshmi, 1998). Age related increase in the hydrogen peroxide concentration in the tissues leads to decrease in CAT activity and cause oxidative stress in the tissues.

It may be because of high reactive oxygen metabolites production especially O₂⁻ and H₂O₂ during aging process. Evidences suggest that O₂⁻ itself affect directly the CAT activity (Kono and Fridovich, 1982). It is also been reported that CAT is inactivated by hydroxyl radical (Piegeolet and Corbisier, 1990). The increased rate of reactive oxygen metabolites production frequently elicits, as a response, an increase in the level of antioxidants. Under high rate of free radicals input, the enzyme inactivation prevails and the enzymatic activities are reduced leading to autocatalysis of oxidative damage process (Escobar *et al.*, 1996; Ray and Husain, 2002). Furthermore, iron is an essential co-factor in the catalase enzyme. An iron deficiency would not only impair oxygen transport in the body, but also compromise the body's antioxidant capacity by lowering catalase activity in cell (Halliwell and Gutteridge, 1999; Powers *et al.*, 2004). If the animals take regularly the Red Grape the activity of CAT would increase. Red Grape may capture the age induced hydrogen peroxides before escaping it from the cell and breakdown them to water and oxygen. In this way Red Grape Extract treatment can maintain the ample catalase activity in the hepatic tissue under age induced oxidative stress condition. The

Table-3: Changes in Glutathione (GSH) activity due to Nicotine treatment (Nt), Red Grape Extract treatment (RGEt) and interaction of the both (Nt+RGEt) for a period of 2 months over the control in Liver tissue of male albino rats of young (3 months) and old (18 months) age groups. Values are expressed in n moles of glutathione/ gm/ wet wt of tissue.

Name of the tissue	Young				Old			
	Control	Nt	RGEt	Nt+RGEt	Control	Nt	RGEt	Nt+RGEt
Liver	178.19 ±7.87	159.81** ±6.54 (-10.31)	189.95** ±6.68 (+6.59)	180.31@ ±7.09 (+1.40)	167.56 ±5.44	157.50** ±4.58 (-6.00)	182.04** ±3.96 (+8.64)	171.25@ ±5.50 (+2.20)

All the values are ± SD of six individual observations.

Values in parentheses denote per cent change over respective control.

* Values are significant at P < 0.05: ** Values are significant at P < 0.01: @ Values are non-significant.

upregulation in CAT activity was found with response of combination (Nt+RGEt) in both age groups of rats. The combination treatment (Nt+RGEt) augmented CAT activity in the liver, suggesting that Red Grape extract treatment (RGEt) may help to develop a resistance in the liver to cope with nicotine induced oxidative injury and maintain the antioxidant system.

Glutathione:

In the present study the Glutathione content was significantly decreased ($P < 0.01$) in both age groups (young and old) of nicotine treated rats (young by -10.31 %; old by -6.00 %) when compared to the control rats. In Red Grape extract treated rats of both age groups (young and old) significantly an increase ($P < 0.01$) was observed when compared to the control rats (young by 6.59 %; old by 8.64 %). In the combination treatment (Nt+RGEt) non significantly an increase was observed when compared to the control rats of both age groups. (Table-3).

In the present study we found that the administration of nicotine showing the decreased in GSH activity in the liver tissue. Similar studies have been reported by several authors. Chennaiah *et al.*, (2006) reported due to nicotine treatment GSH activity was decrease in the muscle tissue. EI- Sokkary *et al.*, (2007) reported chronic administration of nicotine the GSH activity was decreased in the rat liver, lung and kidney. Sener *et al.*, (2005) reported chronic administration of nicotine the GSH activity was decreased in the rat tissues. Nicotine is oxidized primarily into its metabolite cotinine in the liver (Sastry *et al.*, 1995), generates free radicals/ROS in tissues and induces oxidative tissue injury (Ashakumary and Vijayammal, 1996). The depletion of hepatic GSH content seems to indicate the enhanced generation of reactive metabolites due to nicotine metabolism in the liver and oxidative tissue injury.

Similar changes in GSH activity was reported in various toxic conditions by varies authors in various tissues. Chronic ethanol consumption significantly depleted the GSH concentration in the hepatic tissue of different mammals like, rats

(Mahendran and Shyamala Devi, 2001; Kim *et al.*, 2003) mice (Zhou *et al.*, 2002) and man (Kannan *et al.*, 2004; Das and Vasudevan, 2005a). One important antioxidant that is affected by alcohol is glutathione. Liver cells contain an abundance of glutathione, especially with in structures called mitochondria, where most of each cell's energy is generated. The key enzymes in mitochondria are certain cytochromes that are integral components of inner mitochondrial membrane. Glutathione is not synthesized in mitochondria; adequate concentrations of glutathione are maintained there by active transport from the cytoplasm through the mitochondrial membrane. Alcohol interferes with the transport of GSH through membranes, leading to its depletion from mitochondria. The resulting GSH deficiency may permit mitochondrial damage and cell death by means of unimpeded lipid peroxidation (Maher, 1997; Zhou *et al.*, 2002). The decrease in GSH concentration in mitochondria would thus be highly responsible for ROS generation and the structural and functional damage in this organelle (Kannan *et al.*, 2004). The decrease in GSH / CSSG ratio in the hepatic tissue of ethanol fed rats and inhibition of GR activity are indicative of ethanol induced oxidative stress in the hepatic tissue. Depletion of hepatic GSH by chronic ethanol ingestion induced oxidative stress is well reputed.

In the present study the GSH activity was increased in both age groups supplemented with Red Grape extract treatment (RGEt) in the liver tissue of rat. Moreover, the percent elevation of GSH was more pronounced in old age group of rats compared to the young group of rats. Increased GSH content with Red Grape Extract treatment (RGEt) may also due to the increase in the synthesis of precursors for GSH formation and increase the γ -Glutamyl- Cystineglycine enzyme, which is very essential for the GSH. The synthesis and degradation of GSH is referred as the γ -Glutamyl cycle. This cycle small responsible for the enhanced GSH concentration in the hepatic tissue with Red Grape extracts treatment.

Age related an alteration in the levels of reduced glutathione seems to be very complicated. Decreased tissue concentrations of GSH have been reported in several diseased states and are associated with an increase risk to oxidative stress (Bray and Taylor, 1993). GSH decrease may be due to increased oxidation of GSH or decreased in the synthesis of GSH and low decreased availability of precursors for GSH formation. Low glutathione reductase activity may also contribute to the lower levels of GSH in the tissues (Jhansi Lakshmi, 1998). Vohra *et al.*, (2001) reported the decreased glutathione peroxides and glutathione reductase activities in old age animals, indicate inadequate concentrations of GSH for their action in the tissues. De and Darad, (1991) reported the reduced levels of GSH in the hepatic tissue confirm an increased susceptibility to damage with age.

Khalindhar Basha *et al.*, (2013) reported the similar studies on kidney tissue, the Glutathione content (GSH) was reduced in nicotine treated rats and enhanced was observed in the Red grape extract treated rats in the both age groups. However in the combination treatment non significant increase was observed. The reduced antioxidants with nicotine treatment were recovered with combination treatment in both ages. The combination treatment (Nt+RGEt) has the beneficial effect by enhancing the decreased antioxidants in the hepatic tissue. These results clearly indicate that the combination treatment for a period of 2 month would provide the favorable, condition to the cells by decrease the

nicotine and improving their antioxidant aging caused oxidative stress capacity and / or decreased the nicotine and aging caused oxidative stress conditions in the hepatic tissue.

Glutathione peroxidase:

In the present study the glutathione peroxidase activity was significantly decreased ($P < 0.01$) in both age groups (young and old) of nicotine treated rats (young by -37.36 %; old by -25.19%) when compared to the control rats. In Red Grape Extract treated rats of both age groups (young and old) significantly an increase ($P < 0.01$) was observed when compared to the control rats (young by 5.04 %; old by 9.48 %). In the combination treatment (Nt+RGEt) non significantly an increase was observed when compared to the control rats of both age groups. (Table.4).

The present study reveals that the activity of glutathione peroxidase was decreased in nicotine treated rats in both age groups. Similar studies have been reported by several authors due to nicotine, hepatic GPx activity was decreased in mice (Vijayan and Helen, 2007), Wistar rats (Avti *et al.*, 2006). The decreased GSH-Px activity in the current investigation may disturb the glutathione (GSH) homeostasis in the liver cell and ultimately it leads to the damage of hepatocytes. Several studies has been reported by varies authors in different toxic conditions. Kazeem *et al.*, (2011) reported the GSH-Px activity was decreased in the hepatic tissue due to nicotine toxicity. Khalindhar Basha *et al.*, (2013) reported in the kidney tissue the Glutathioneperoxidase was reduced in nicotine

Table-4: Changes in Glutathione peroxidase (Gpx) activity due to Nicotine treatment (Nt) ,Red Grape Extract treatment (RGEt) and interaction of the both (Nt+RGEt) for a period of 2 months over the control in Liver tissue of male albino rats of young (3 months) and old (18 months) age groups. Values are expressed in μ moles of thioether formed/ mg protein/min.

Name of the tissue	Young				Old			
	Control	Nt	RGEt	Nt+RGEt	Control	Nt	RGEt	Nt+RGEt
Liver	119.27 ± 7.07	74.71** ± 4.53 (-37.36)	125.29** ± 7.18 (+5.04)	123.06 [@] ± 5.92 (+3.17)	96.93 ± 6.07	72.51** ± 4.58 (-25.19)	106.12** ± 5.70 (+9.48)	103.94 [@] ± 4.23 (+7.23)

All the values are \pm SD of six individual observations.

Values in parentheses denote per cent change over respective control.

* Values are significant at $P < 0.05$; ** Values are significant at $P < 0.01$; @ Values are non-significant.

treated rats. Ostrowska *et al.*, (2004) reported the decreased GSH-Px activity at a significant level in rat brain tissue for a period of 4 weeks ethanol intoxication. Recently Das and Vasudevan, (2005a) reported the decreased GSH-Px activity in the liver homogenate with a series of ethanol treatments like, 0.8g, 1.2g, 1.6g and 2.0g / kg body weight for a period of 4 weeks, our result also agreement with this. Decrease in GSH-Px activity may be due to either free radical dependant inactivation of enzyme or depletion of its co-substrate i.e., GSH and NADPH in the nicotine treatments. Similar studies, Santanukar Mahapatra *et al.*, (2008) reported smoking decreases the Glutathione peroxidase in the serum of mans. GPx works nonspecifically to scavenge and decompose excess hydro peroxides including H₂O₂, which may prevalent under oxidative stress (Somani *et al.*, 1996). In this study, decreased GPx activity seems to indicate the smoking induced oxidative stress. The decrease level of GSH and activity of GSH-dependent enzyme i.e.GPx, GR. Liver GSH content after alcohol administration was found to decrease due to increased over utilization by the hepatocytes. Due to non-availability of GSH under ethanol oxidative stress condition, a decrease in the activity of GSH-Px has been observed in the hepatocytes. Depletion of glutathione will render the enzyme GSH-Px inactivation and / or less active (Mahendran and Shyamala Devi, 2001). GSH-Px catalysis the reduction of lipid peroxides or hydrogen peroxides using reduced glutathione as a substrate, thus providing a line of metabolism against ethanol induced oxidative stress (Albert II and Ren, 2003). Decreased hepatic GSH-Px activity due to ethanol consumption indicate low profile in scavenging the hydrogen peroxide and lipid peroxides, which may be due to oxidative inactivation of the enzyme (Pigeolet *et al.*, 1990). The decreased GSH-Px activity due to alcohol treatment was reported by several authors in the hepatic tissue of rat (Bykova and Zhukova, 1991; Dinu and Zamfir, 1991). Ethanol can also induce oxidative stress indirectly by reducing intracellular antioxidant capacity, such as the levels of glutathione peroxidase. In rats, chronic ethanol consumption decreased significantly glutathione peroxides

activity and caused a parallel increase of oxidative modification of proteins in hepatocytes (Oh *et al.*, 1997; Bailey *et al.*, 2001).

The results obtained from the present study reveals that Red Grape Extract treatment (RGEt), enhanced the hepatic glutathione peroxidase activity to in both age groups of rats when compared to their respective controls. Similar studies has been reported in the kidney tissue in Red grape extract treated rats the GSH-Px activity was enhanced in the both age groups(Khalindhar Basha *et al.*,2013). GSH-Px activity increased in hepatic tissue at a high level indicating an efficient elimination of organic peroxides (Husain and Somani, 1997a). By accepting an electron from the peroxide (or donating a hydrogen ion), GSH is oxidized to half of disulphide (GSSH). This reaction is catalyzed by Se-containing GSH-Px enzyme. The elevation of glutathione peroxidase activity due to Red Grape Extract treatment suggests an increased capacity to handle hydroperoxides in the tissues. It appears that Red Grape extract treatment provide the required substrate for a high increase in the GSH-Px activity. In addition, tissues with oxidative stress showed increased levels of SOD and GSH-Px, similar to the results obtained for SOD in this studies, the Red Grape Extract treatment induced upregulation of GSH-Px activity, appears that SOD and GSH-Px are actively involving in decomposing the oxygen derived free radicals in the hepatic tissue of old rats. The reason for higher GSH-Px activity in Red Grape Extract treatment rats may be due to higher production of ROS and increased activity of SOD in the rats. However, the available reports suggest the fact that higher SOD activity may be responsible in part, for higher GSH-Px activity (Ray and Husain, 2002).

The specific activity of GSH-Px was remarkably decreased in old rats compared to the young rats. With the aging, the GPx activity was decreased in different animals and different tissues reported by several authors. The age related decrease in hepatic GSH-Px activity in the current study was supported by earlier reports also (Cand and Verdetti, 1989; Matsuo *et al.*, 1992). Vohra *et*

al., (2001) reported both cytosolic and mitochondrial GSH-Px activities were decreased in different brain regions of 32 months old guinea pigs. There appears to be an inter relationship between the activity of SOD and GSH-Px. The deficiency of SOD has been shown to be associated with decrease in the activity of GSH-Px vice-versa (Michiels *et al.*, 1994). Both Se-dependent and Se-independent GSH-Px were decreased in old rats compared with the young rats. The production of free radicals and other reactive oxygen species are believed to increase with age in most tissues (Lawler and Powers, 1998 and Madhuri and Viveka Vardhani, 2015). These increased free radicals especially hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) may be responsible for the low activity of hepatic glutathione peroxidase in older rats. The decreased SOD activity in old rats which was also reported in the present study may also be responsible for the lower GSH-Px activity, because of their interrelation in detoxifying the toxic radicals. This age related decrease in hepatic GSH-Px activity was augmented with Red Grape extract compared to control rats. Thus, Red Grape Extract play a prominent role in preventing nicotine induced oxidative stress by promoting the GSH-Px activity in nicotine hepatic tissue in young and as well as old age rats.

CONCLUSION

To be precise, the findings of the present investigation suggest that 2 months Red grape extract treatment with the selected mgs (50 mg/kg/ body weight) that was adapted may be beneficial in countering the age associated and nicotine induced alterations in antioxidant enzyme system.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am very much grateful to the UGC-MRP Fellow, New Delhi for providing the financial support (UGC-MRP Letter No.39-612//2010 (SR), dated 10-01-2011) sanctioned by Dept. of Zoology. S. V. University, Tirupati., and my humble thanks to my Research supervisor, Dr.

K. Chennaiah. Asst professor, Department of Zoology S.V.University, Tirupati.

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DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7252629>

Received: 8 January 2015;

Accepted; 21 February 2015;

Available online : 6 March 2015
